

Mathnawi ma'nawi

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The Ottoman Empire, which valued and promoted Persian culture, was itself a bridge of civilizations upon which the Persian literary corpus reached its westernmost geographical extent in the Balkans. Bosnia and Herzegovina and its environs (the Balkans) were not simply a part of the Islamic cultural orbit, but contributed actively to the Persian literary tradition. In addition to its artistic and literary character, the Persian literary corpus was also highly valued for its moral and didactic education, as well as Tasavvuf's spiritual teachings. Persian literary tradition appears to have been a trans-Islamic mediator of important works of Sufism. Above all was Rumi's Mathnawī-i ma'nawī (or Mathnawi), a text which motivated many in the broader Ottoman Empire and, more specifically, Bosnia to learn the Persian language. The Mawlāviyya order, naturally, encouraged the reading and interpreting of the text. In Ottoman society, outside the Ottoman madrasas, Mathnawi regularly entered the tafsir domain as an alter-exegesis, which founded a different hermeneutics with a different register and which offered semantic possibilities beyond those reproduced within the academies of tafsir. Echoes of this past continue to reverberate in the contemporary Muslim culture of the Balkans. Therefore, in these regions, even today, classical Sufi Persian works are still read, especially Rumi's Mathnawi both among educated individuals and in Sufi tekkes (lodges) and khalkas (circles) outside the tekke. This work was not read independently, but in groups with interpretation. This encyclopedia's entry seeks to present to an English-speaking audience the activity of Bosnian interpreters of Rumi's Mathnawi in the Ottoman era and post-Ottoman era, as well as the continuity of interpreting of Mathnawī ma'nawī in modern-day Bosnia and Herzegovina up today. Therefore, this entry will introduce a number of Bosnian interpreters of Mathnawī ma'nawī who contributed to this intellectual endeavor.

Date Range: 1462 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Bosnia and Herzegovina

Region tags: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Balkans, Europe, Southern Europe, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Today, modern Bosnia and Herzegovina was part of the former Yugoslavia and, further into the past, part of the former Ottoman Empire, more precisely the Bosnian Eyalet. Major cities include: Sarajevo, Mostar, Tuzla, Visoko, Livno and Busovača.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Gačanin, Sabaheta, "Katedra Mesneviye Derviš-paše Bajezidagića u Mostaru", *Život i djelo i vrijeme Derviš-paše Bajezidagića*, BZK Preporod, Gradsko društvo Mostar, Fakultet humanističkih nauka,

Mostar, 2005, 117-120.

- Source 1: Gačanin, Sabaheta, „Mevlana Dželaluddin Rumi o ljubavi i u ljubavi”/Mevlana Jalaluddin Rumi on Love and in love, *Živa baština*, vol. VI, br. 20 (2020), 40-51.
- Source 2: Gačanin, Sabaheta, „The Persian Literary Tradition in Ottoman Bosnia and Its Environs”, *Brill: Journal of Persianate Studies* 15 (2022), 85-120.
- Source 3: Gadžo, Šaban, “Tradicija kazivanja tumačenja Mesnevijske u Sarajevu i nekim drugim mjestima u BiH”, *Behar* 116 (2013), 3-13.
- Source 1: Abedpour, Saeid, Tradicija mesnevihanstva u Bosni i Hercegovini, *Znakovi vremena* 45-46(2009), 232-246.
- Source 2: Beglerović, Samir, Tri različita pristupa intelektualnom naslijeđu Mawlāne Ğalāl Ad-Dīna Rūmīja, *Behar*, vol. XXII, 116(2013), 86-89.
- Source 3: Evlija Čelebi, Putopis. Odlomci o jugoslavenskim zemljama, prevod, uvod i komentar Hazim Šabanović, *Svjetlost*, Sarajevo 1967.
- Source 1: Hazreti Mevlana Dželaluddin Rumi. Mesnevijska i mesnevihani u Sarajevu, *Behar*, časopis za kulturu i društvena pitanja, god. XXII br. 116 (2013), Kulturno društvo Bošnjaka Hrvatske Preporod, Zagreb.
- Source 2: Mevlana Dželaluddin Rumi, Mesnevijska I-II, Tekijski odbor Nakšibendijsko Mevlevijske tekije na Mlinima u Sarajevu (Katedra Mesnevijske), Sarajevo 1987.
- Source 3: Dželaluddin Rumi, Mesnevijska, 1-3, s perzijskog preveo i komentare napisao Ahmed Mešić, *Behram-begova medresa*, Tuzla 2016.
- Source 1: Hafizović, Rešid, Temeljni tokovi sufizma, *Bemust*, Sarajevo 1999.
- Source 2: Trako, Salih, “Predavanje Mesnevijske i mesnevihani u Sarajevu”, *Anali GHB*, knj. XIII-XIV (1987), 221-226.
- Source 3: Hasandedić, Hivzija, Mostarski vakifi i njihovi vakufi, Mostar 2000.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/CommentaryOfTheMathnawiOfRumiByYunusPatelVol.1/page/n1/mode/2up>
- Source 1 Description: <https://archive.org/details/in.gov.ignca.11970/page/n7/mode/2up>
- Source 2 URL: <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://traditionalhikma.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/Rumi-The-Mathnawi-of-Jalalu%E2%80%99ddin-Rumi-trans.-Nicholson-1.pdf>

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: Mathnawi was read, translated and interpreted orally in a narrow circle of listeners, mostly in Mawlavi tekkes. Even today, the tradition of interpreting the Mathnawi is current in Bosnia and

Herzegovina, in tekke and circles that are formed around the mathnevikhans by listening to the oral presentation of the interpreters (mathnawikhans) of the Mathnawi. However, interpretations of mathnawikhans in Bosnia and Herzegovina are starting to be published, as well as a special annual Šeb-i arus in which, among other things, interpretations of a few verses from the Mathnawi are published.

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Overwritten

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: We are talking about the interpretation of the Mathnawi text.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: The translation of the text of Mathnawi as well as the studies on Mathnawi, have the possibility to receive funding from state budget sources. They are mostly financed from personal publishing or from citizens' associations.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Yes

Notes: Interpretation of the Mathnawi was exclusively through oral lectures in narrow circles. In modern times, the circle of interested listeners has expanded, and interpretations of Bosnian mathnawikhans are also published for readers.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

Notes: Mathnawi ma'nawi consists of anecdotes, apologies, quotations from the Qur'an, prophetic traditions, reflections, hermeneutics of verses, mystical sayings, legends, sayings and teachings of Sufi greats, fables and parables with numerous literary digressions, allusions and associative accumulation of images for the contemplation of those versed in spiritual knowledge, by which Jalaluddin Rumi encompassed all perspectives of the spiritual teachings of Islam.

↳ Inspired by high god?

– Yes

Notes: It could be said that Mathnawi speech is inspired by Allah. Mawlana quoted, explained and interpreted more than five hundred Quranic verses and about 750 hadiths of God's prophet in the Mathnawa, either directly or by allusion.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: There are institutions that deal with Islamic education, primarily related to the Book and Tradition and other disciplines related to it. Mathnawi interpretation belongs to informal Islamic education.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

Notes: The interpretation of Mathnawi could be held in tekkes, mosques, private houses and halkas and was not conditioned to be in institutions.

– Yes

Notes: The interpretation of Mathnawi takes place mainly outside institutions, in an informal environment, such as tekkies, mosques and in smaller circles, which are

considered exclusive.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– No

Notes: The text of the Mathnawi is available to all researchers, who can process its material by studying it to draw lessons, and especially to those who have received special permission to interpret from their predecessors (shaykhs).

– No

Notes: Reading and interpretation of the Mathnawi, especially its translations, which are also available today in the Bosnian language, are available to students and researchers.

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– Yes

Notes: The Salafi-Wahhabi school considers the Mathnawi to be full of myths and does not consider it a reference in religious discourse, while the moderate Ahli-Sunnah and Sufi schools consider this book to be one of the important sources of spiritual education for Muslims because it provides well-illustrated examples for the spiritual maturation of individuals. Because man's life is not mere duration (animality) or just concern for everyday life, but is an internal task of spiritual and moral self-awareness.

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– Yes

Notes: At some historical moment it will happen, when all differences will be reconciled.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: There were individuals (mathnawikhān) who interpreted the Mathnawi ma'nawi text, but they had to fulfill special conditions for doing so. If the mathnawikhan is related to the Mawlawi tariqat (he did not have to be a sheikh of the tariqat), then he had to undergo special spiritual training. If they are not tied to the tariqat, then they had to be morally eligible, educated, with linguistic competence (Persian and Arabic language, even Turkish if they used Turkish language commentaries) and instructed in the various contexts within which the mathnawikhanī tradition (cultural history of tasawwuf) was realized, Islamic philosophy, ilm al-kalam and others). - We highlight here special personalities, whose names are associated with the interpretation of Mathnawi ma'nawi, in the 20th century, Behaudin Efendi Sikirić (1860 - 1934), sheikh of the Nakshbandi tekke and muderris; translated and interpreted the Mathnawi in Nadmlini tekke in Sarajevo, since 1905; a muderris and mufti Muhammed Efendi Korkut (1824 - 1920), translated and interpreted Mathnawi in Travnik; Qadi Ahmed Efendi Mešić (1916-1994) taught Mathnawi in Visoko (1972 to 1976), and then in Tuzla (1990 to 1994), three volumes of Mathnawi were published with his translation and interpretation; - the prominent mathnawikhans in Sarajevo are: Džemaludin Čaušević (1870 - 1938), reisul-ulema in Bosnia and Herzegovina, mathnawikhan and sheikh of the Mawlawi Tariqat, interpreted Mathnawi 17 years

(1942 - 1959); the famous merchant and mathnawikhan Haji Mujaga Merhemić, interpreted the Mathnawi in the tekke in Bendbaša and then by force in his house, he taught derses of Mathnawi for 17 years (1942-1959); Haji Fejzullah Efendi Hadžibajrić (1913 - 1990), sheikh of the Qaderiyya tariqat, researcher and librarian, mathnawikhan for 23 years (1965 - 1988) in Sarajevo; Haji Hafiz Halid Efendi Hadžimulić (1915 - 2011) imam and librarian, mathnawikhan for 23 years (1988-2011); - in the 20th century known mathnawikhans: Haji Hafiz Mehmed Karahodžić (1962-), interpreting Mathnawi in Sarajevo since 2011 up today, his lectures were first in Bakr-baba Mosque then in Mawlawi tekke, lectures well attended; Fuad Hadžiomerović (1974) held lectures of Mathnawi in Tuzla; and another mathnawikhan, a woman, dr. Mubina Moker (1965-), holding lectures of interpretation of Mathnawi in Naqshbandi tekke Masudiyya in Kaćuni (near Sarajevo) since 2020 up today.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– No

Notes: The Mathnawikhans were men, as were the listeners, middle-aged or older. In the modern age, mathnavikhans and listeners are of a younger age, both male and female. Among the mathnawikhans of contemporary Bosnia and Herzegovina, there are also women. Example of dr. Mubina Moker, mathnavikhan in Kaćuna tekke, since 2020.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

Notes: The Mathnawikhans were men, as were the listeners, middle-aged or older. In the modern age, mathnawikhans and listeners are of a younger age, both male and female.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– Yes

Notes: In the case of Mathnawi interpretation, the individuals who interpret the Mathnawi are called Mathnawīkhān, derived from the Persian word (mathnawī+khān=Mathnawi+learner, reader, reciter). Those who know Mathnawi by heart are called hafizi Mathnawi. It is recorded that Hafiz Mathnawi (according to Halid ef. Salihagić) lived in Fojnica (a small town northwest of Sarajevo), a shoemaker by profession.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, it is the Holy Qur'an for Muslims.

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the cannon as it is currently understood?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The Mathnawi is written in the Persian language, this book does not have the sanctity that the Qur'an carries, because its texts are subject to addition or subtraction, unlike the Qur'an. In the Sufi Muslim literary discourse, Rumi's Mathnawi, although it did not belong to the genre of formal tafsir but to literature, is considered one of the two or three most important texts (and for many the only most important text) that could be used to interpret the Qur'an in a wider geographical area.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Notes: Mathnawi is one of the sources that are considered and approved by Sufis (Ahli Sunnat and Shia), and therefore it is approved by almost all Sufis, regardless of their scientific level. Mathnawi, apart from Sufis, has a transglobal popularity in various other segments of the social community.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Notes: Every person needs to examine himself and learn to listen and act according to the instructions of the inner voice of the heart filled with love, in which the power of divine energy is hidden. A general principle is valid, based on the presentation of a model of a just person who can coexist with everyone regardless of religion or race.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Notes: Mathnawi represents an ocean of gnosis that hides the overall Sufi wisdom, sung on the idea of Tawhid and addressed to all people of the universe, without distinction of religion, nation and skin color; and the condition is only honesty and love.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: Mathnawi is a motivational text.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: The text itself is versed in the mathnawi literary form

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: The Mathnawi manuscripts were of different ages. In the past, Mathnawi interpreters (mathnawikhans) used available manuscripts that were rare, because they were voluminous and too expensive to copy, but manuscripts of Mathnawi fragments were common and available. Today, the following Mathnawi manuscripts are preserved in Bosnia and Herzegovina: GHB R-3066 volumes I and II from 891/1486), GHB R-2599 volume IV from 1076/1666; R-8516 volume V from the 16th century; and fragments from individual volumes R-928/1, R-2559; R-4316 and others. The copyist of the Qur'an, Dervish Muhamed Bošnjak (1647/48), copied the entire Mathnawi for the needs of the dervishes of the Mawlawi tekke in Bendbaša, Sarajevo.

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

Notes: The Mathnawi is one of the most extensive Sufi literary works in the Persian language. Its authentic copies consist of six volumes and 25,628 couplets. Mathnawi ma'nawi is probably the most read, most recited and most studied Tasawwuf text in intellectual history. It is woven from anecdotes, apologies, quotations from the Qur'an, prophetic traditions, reflections, hermeneutics of verses, mystical sayings, legends, sayings and teachings of Sufi greats, fables and parables with numerous literary digressions, allusions and associative accumulation of images for contemplation directed to spiritual knowledge, with which Mawlana Jalaluddin Rumi encompassed all perspectives of the spiritual teachings of Islam. In his deliberations, he touches on all relevant matters related to man and his existence in the universe. He gives primacy to the essence of things, while existence has a secondary role, the role of an accident that is attributed to the essence. Among other things, he indirectly discusses physics and psychology, as well as issues of eschatology and spiritual union. Through his ultra-sensitive and ultra-rational Sufi experience,

Mawlana Rumi connects spirituality, rationality and universal morality in a special way through statements and interpretations.

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– Yes

Notes: Through the stories, there are descriptions of ritual practice, direct or allusive references to ritual practice.allusion to a ritual practice appears.

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: There is some debate over the authorship of the seventh volume of the Mathnawi, which is believed not to have been written by Mawlana Rumi.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The complete Mathnawi consists of about 26,000 verses divided into six volumes. Therefore, only fragments of this voluminous work are often translated and interpreted.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary? (Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: The stories include the names of prophets, kings, great men, cities and other proper names that could be indexed.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: Various personalities of different origins, Arabs, Persians, Turks, Greeks, etc. are mentioned in the stories.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Mawlana Rumi gives primacy to the essence of things, while existence has a secondary role, the role of accident that is attributed to the essence. With his verses and sayings, Rumi interprets secrets from the three most important kingdoms - Revelation, the universe and the soul, through whose interpretation he reveals and more closely explains knowledge about creation, cosmology and spiritual psychology, which is a fundamental theme in all forms of Islamic science and knowledge.

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: By understanding the true order of things, a person in the regions of the soul will receive knowledge about the nature of Reality, which results in understanding and wisdom of living in harmony with other people and nature.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Notes: This question is fundamentally related to Sufi thought among Muslims. Mawlana like other Sufis who experienced the truths of the World of Secrets and were versed in spiritual knowledge avoided describing the nature of spiritual lights and their flashes. Although they admitted that the truths of the Other World are indescribable, they still searched for the meanings of words that would even slightly hint at the force of their experience. Therefore, they used very complex symbolic language and metaphors.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– No

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

Notes: This topic has been the subject of extensive debate from the beginnings of Sufi Islamic thought to the present day.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– Yes

Notes: Discussions usually take place at the level of scientific research and then confrontation with arguments, although rarely do "honest" Sufis engage in direct debates or discussions.

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– Yes

Notes: Extremists reject dialogue and debate and generally accept the method of exclusion.

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Yes

Notes: Sufis were often exposed to pressure and threats, and were even killed (such as Abu Mansur al-Hallaj and Suhrawardi). Today, the opponents of Sufis are the Salafists, who have banned Sufism in all Zayvi countries.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ What are the historically minority positions?

– Specify: There is no mention of this topic in the obligatory religious texts, because according to the principle of Islam, all people are equal.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Notes: The doctrine of reincarnation is completely foreign to Islam.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not mention the manner of funeral rituals.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: It is possible that burial allusions are present, without formal descriptions.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text talks about people, but also about spiritual beings.

A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The text talks about ordinary people, but also about spiritual beings.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: The text mentions angels, demons, hurries, jinns and everything related to Islamic tradition. Through versed allegorical stories about life, Rumi expresses inexhaustible insight and knowledge about the countless meanings of understanding and living Islam, but also as a Sufi experience that defies meaningful description, i.e. it must be tasted to be known.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Ordinary people can become supernatural themselves after a series of complex spiritual exercises and experiences.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Paranormal events are present in the text as allusions to the spiritual states of the described characters.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
– Yes

↳ Food
– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s)
– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s)
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

Notes: All practices other than heterosexuality are banned.

↳ Adultery

– Yes

↳ Incest

– Yes

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– No

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– Yes

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

Notes: Particularly with regards to worshipping God.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

Notes: Sorcery is forbidden.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– Yes

Notes: Although it is only stressed in relation to worship and prayer.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Yes

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: If we consider angels as supernatural beings, they are the ones who carry out divine punishment for those who deserve it

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: If we consider angels as supernatural beings, they are the ones who bring reward to those who deserve it.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– I don't know

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– I don't know

↳ At some other time [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

Notes: The text does not directly address this issue, because the time of the end of the world for Muslims belongs only to Divine knowledge.

↳ Divine judgment event

– No

Notes: Divine judgment is a part of Islam and Mawlana addresses this through his verses.

↳ Restoration of the world

– No

Notes: Resurrection is part of Muslim's belief, the book refers to it directly and indirectly through instructive stories.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– No

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

↳ Other form of eschatology?

– Specify: The Mathnawi is a collection of the Mawlana's gnostic, ethical and educational thoughts chanted after education, study, research, teaching, spiritual journey and spiritual practice, which spanned his entire life.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive

– Yes

Notes: Virtuous people will enjoy eternal life in heaven, but in this earthly mortal life, all will face the same fate (death).

↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive

– No

Notes: The complete destruction of this worldly life is part of the Muslim beliefs.

↳ All members of the sample region will survive

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton

– No

Notes: There are inevitably people who will fall under Satan's control and be with him in eternal hell.

↳ Other survival condition [specify]

–Specify: Muslims believe that everything will disappear and that only God remains.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

Notes: Family values are fundamental values for Sufism because they are part of general Islamic values.

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

Notes: Liberation from lust is the form of liberation desired by the Sufis.

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

Notes: Power in a moral sense is present in the characters in the text, as well as nobility in a moral sense, not in a social sense.

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

Notes: The goal is to achieve spiritual beauty, not physical or sensual beauty.

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: Love is at the center of everything and acts as an uplifting experience, through which the virtue of the highest Truth is understood, received and tested.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not propagate this, but certain figures in the text practiced it as part of Sufi ethics.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– Yes

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Faith Elect

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Spiritual Elect

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– A Faith Elect

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– Yes

Notes: The practice of charity (sadaqa) is quite prevalent among Sufi groups and individual actors. While voluntary charity (sadaqa) may be given in an ad-hoc fashion, more formal mechanisms exist as well. They often include the establishment of a charitable endowment (waqf) that provides specific services based on the stipulations of the contract. Services may include food distribution, lodging, education, religious training, or medical care. These acts are often referred to as 'ongoing charity' (sadaqa jarriyya) as individuals continue to gain spiritual benefit in the afterlife for continuing to provide material support for this world.

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Notes: Mathnawi advocates Qur'anic anthropology, which starts from the integral man as God's creation, whose duty is to strive in addition to spiritual perfection and good deeds, because without a

good soul, there is no good and characterful man who cares for the individual and collective destiny of man. So the text through stories directly and indirectly teaches and encourages people to duty and care for other people and their needs. Thus, among the messages of the Mathnawi text is the pursuit of ethics, which regulates relationships between people in the best possible way.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Notes: Among the messages of the text are certainly the spreading of all the values of solidarity and concern for other people.

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: All ethical values of human solidarity are promoted.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: All Muslim communities that study tasawwuf rely on this text as one of their sources.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Notes: The text of Mathnawi is available to all scholars, including non-Muslims.

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: There is no gender discrimination in relation to those who work on the text Mathnawikhan (interpreter of Mathnawi) can be any person who has ethical, moral and educational competences for interpretation.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: Mawlana Rumi was devoted to peace, he criticized war in numerous verses, since he was a witness to numerous wars and a witness to the blessings of peace between wars. Therefore, he passionately advocated peace and was a supporter of the coexistence of different religions.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

Notes: Through his verses, Mawlana Rumi indirectly touches on food production.

Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– Yes

Notes: In the text, people are advised to do business in a halal way

Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Hunting (including marine animals)

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Mathnawi ma'nawi, Gačanin, Sabaheta. "The Persian Literary Tradition in Ottoman Bosnia and Its Environs" 15, no. 1 (December 22, 2022). <https://doi.org/10.1163/18747167-bja10027>.